

INVESTIGATION OF THE OIL FROM THE FRUITS OF *FERULA ALLIACEA*, BOISS.

BY PRAFULLA KUMAR BOSE AND SACHINDRA NATH DUTT.

The fruits of *F. alliacea* contain 19 per cent of oil and some natural coumarins. The constants of the oil have been determined and its probable composition has been discussed.

Following a scheme for the systematic investigation of plant materials of the *Umbelliferae* order, we took up the present investigation. Although some work on the resin of *F. alliacea* roots have been recorded (Hirschsohn, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1878, 213, 309; Tschrich, *Harze*, 2nd Ed., Vol. I, p. 362), the fruits of this plant do not appear to have been investigated before.

The mature fruits emit a powerful aromatic smell when crushed, apparently due to the presence of a volatile oil. In fact, steam distillation of a petroleum ether extract of the material gave about 0.9% of a colourless oil having a strong sweet smell. The nature of the oil is being investigated.

The oil used in this investigation was extracted from the crushed fruits by light petroleum. The insoluble yellow solid matters were removed, the oil freed from the solvent and dried. Thus isolated, the oil has a yellow colour, a pleasant smell and a bitter taste. The following constants were recorded with a sample of dry oil.

Density at 31.5° (water at 31.5°)	... 0.9156
Refractive index at 40°	... 1.4691
Specific rotation in chloroform at 30° (11.20% soln.)	... +1.94°
Solubility in alcohol at 25°	... 2.55%
Thermal value	... 16°
True Valenta number (acetic acid)	... 74.67°
Maumene test	... 95.06
Bromide test	... nil
Acid value	... 16.6
Saponification value	... 189.62
Ester value	... 173.02
Iodine value (Wijs)	... 90.73
Hypochlorous acid value*	... 19.05
Acetyl value	... 23.56
Reichert-Meissl value (5 g. oil)	... 1.81
Polenske value (5 g. oil)	... 0.25
Total saturated fatty acids (corr.)	... 14.02%
" unsaturated " " "	... 78.08%
Unsaponifiable matter	... 1.96%

* Goewami and Basu, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 905.

An attempt has been made to correlate the above data and explain their significance. The thermal value and Maumene test indicate that the oil is non-drying. This inference is further supported by the iodine value. The solubility of the oil in alcohol is apparently due to the presence of glycerides of hydroxy-acids and the high acetyl value lends support to this suggestion. The low Reichert and Polenske values may be due to rancidity and decomposition. As a matter of fact high acid value is associated with rancidity. The absence of tetra-, hexa-, and octa-bromides in the bromination products of the total fatty acids indicates absence of polyunsaturated acids, although it should be mentioned that small quantities of higher unsaturated acids may escape detection by this method which is never quantitative in character.

The 'solid' saturated acids (yield 17.5%), obtained by the lead salt-ether method, had an iodine value of 20 showing that appreciable quantities of unsaturated acids are present along with the 'saturated' acids. A repetition of the process of separation did not much alter the I.V. It is, therefore, evident that the 'saturated' acids must contain some unsaturated acids like erucic or petrosilenic acid, the lead salts of which are insoluble in ether and consequently they group together with the 'saturated' acid fraction. It is noteworthy that petrosilenic acid has been found to occur in the seed oil of some plants belonging to the same Natural Order as *F. alliacea* (Dean, "Utilization of Fats," 1938, p. 93).

The alcoholysis of the oil was carried by the method described by Goswami and Ramanujam (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 413). The methyl esters from 50 g. of the oil gave the following fractions. on distillation at 16 mm.*

Fractions	...	I.	II.	III.	IV.	V
B.p.	...	Up to 100°	100-130°	130-155°	155-210°	210-20°
Yield	...	0.85	0.42	2.4	0	32.2 g.

Fraction I consisted mainly of essential oil. Fractions II and III were not further examined for want of sufficient material. Myristic acid (b.p. of methyl ester, 167°/15 mm.) and palmitic acid (b.p. of methyl ester, 196°/15 mm.) are apparently absent. Fraction V, which constituted the bulk of the distillate, had an I.V. of 86.16 and gave no solid product on bromination of the acid obtained from this fraction. The b.p. as also the I.V. is in agreement with those of methyl oleate.

* During fractionation yellow solids separated out from the distilling liquid,

The natural coumarins present in *F. alliacea* as also the volatile oil will form the subject of a future communication.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Preliminary Experiments.—The fruits of *F. alliacea* were obtained from Poona. They were identified by Dr. K. Biswas of the Royal Botanic Garden, Sibpur and by Professor A. Das-Gupta, Calcutta, to both of whom we are greatly indebted. The fruits were coarsely powdered and 50 g. out of the whole lot were successively extracted with different solvents in a Soxhlet. The solvents were removed in each case and the nature and quantities of the extracts were noted.

(i) Petroleum ether (b.p. 30–50°) extracted 20% of the material. The extract was a yellow oil containing a granular yellow solid, which amounted to nearly 1·2% of the fruits.

(ii) The ether extract was a brownish oil having little solid matter and amounted to 1·4%.

(iii) The chloroform extract (yield 2%) had a similar appearance.

(iv) The alcoholic extract (yield 3·7%) was a dark greyish brown tarry mass.

Extraction of the Oil.—For a large scale extraction, light petroleum was used and the extraction was continued briskly during 20 hours in a Soxhlet apparatus. The solvent was then removed on the water-bath and finally under reduced pressure in a slow current of air at about 70°. The oil was allowed to stand at room temperature for several days when a yellow granular solid separated out. The oil was separated by filtration and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate during a week. The clear oil, thus obtained, was used in the following experiments (yield 19%).

Essential Oil.—A portion of the above oil was distilled in steam. The distillate was taken up with ether, dried over sodium sulphate and the solvent removed under reduced pressure. The pale yellow oil thus obtained (yield 0·9%) had a pleasant camphoraceous smell.

Thermal Value (Bromine Thermal Test).—This test is a measure of the heat evolved on treating a definite weight (1 g.) of an oil dissolved in a definite volume (10 c.c.) of chloroform with a definite (1 c.c.) volume of bromine. The test was carried out in a Dewar's flask.

Initial temp. of oil and chloroform	... 32°
Final temp. after addition of bromine	... 48°
Hence thermal value	... 16°

True Valenta Number (Acetic Acid).—It was determined by the method of Freyer and Weston ("Handbook of Oils, Fats and Waxes," 1918, Vol. I, p. 76).

Turbidity temp. of oil	... 54.5°
Oleic acid content	... 8.61%
Corrected turbidity temp.	... 74.04°
Turbidity temp. of almond oil	... 72.5°
Oleic acid content	... 3.03%
Corrected turbidity temp.	... 79.37°
Hence true Valenta number	... 74.67°

Maumene Test.—The modified method of Thompson and Ballantyne (*J. Chem. Soc. Ind.*, 1891, 234) was followed.

Initial temp. of oil	... 26°
Final temp. after treatment	... 64.5°
Hence rise of temp.	... 38.50°
Initial temp. of water	... 25°
Final temp. after mixing with H ₂ SO ₄	... 66.5°
Hence rise of temp.	... 40.5°
Therefore, Specific Temperature Reaction	= 95.06

Separation of Solid and Liquid Acids.—8 G. of the oil gave 1.393 g. of 'saturated' acids and 5.969 g. of 'unsaturated' acids. The I.V. of the 'saturated' acid was found to be 19.9. Hence amount of monounsaturated acids present in the saturated acids = 3.48%. Therefore, corrected percentage of saturated acids = 14.02 and corrected percentage of unsaturated acids = 78.08.

The I.V. of the 'unsaturated' acids was found to be 100.6. The 'saturated' acids were obtained as an oil, which solidified on keeping and melted at 29.30°.

We are indebted to Dr. M. N. Goswami for some valuable suggestions in connexion with this investigation.